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ON AN EXPANSION FORMULA FOR THE MULTIVARIABLE I - FUNCTION INVOLVING GENERALIZED LEGENDRE'S ASSOCIATED FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

The authors have established a new expansion formula for multivariable I -function due to Prasad [5] in terms of products of the multivariable I -function and the generalized Legendre's associated function due to Meulenbeld [3]. Some special cases are given in the last.

Keywords:

Multivariable I -function, Generalized Legendre's associated function, Multivariable H -function.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The multivariable I -function introduced by Prasad [5] will be define and represent it in the following manner:

$$I[z_1, \dots, z_r] = I_{p_2, q_2, \dots, p_r, q_r; (p', q') \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)})}^{0, n_2, \dots, 0, n_r; (m', n') \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)})}$$

$$\left[z_1, \dots, z_r \left| \begin{array}{l} (a_{2j}, \alpha_{2j}, \alpha_{2j}^{\prime})_{1, p_2} \dots (\alpha_{rj}, \alpha_{rj}^{\prime}, \alpha_{rj}^{\prime})_{1, p_r} : (a_j, \alpha_j^{\prime})_{1, p} \dots (a_j^{(r)}, \alpha_j^{(r)})_{1, p^{(r)}} \\ (b_{2j}, \beta_{2j}, \beta_{2j}^{\prime})_{1, q_2} \dots (b_{rj}, \beta_{rj}^{\prime}, \beta_{rj}^{\prime})_{1, q_r} : (b_j, \beta_j^{\prime})_{1, q} \dots (b_j^{(r)}, \beta_j^{(r)})_{1, q^{(r)}} \end{array} \right. \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi w)^r} \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_r} \phi_1(s_1) \dots \phi_r(s_r) \psi(s_1, \dots, s_r) z_1^{s_1} \dots z_r^{s_r} ds_1 \dots ds_r \quad (1.1)$$

Where

$$w = \sqrt{-1}$$

$$\phi_i(s_i) = \frac{\prod_{j=1}^{m^{(i)}} \Gamma(b_j^{(i)} - \beta_j^{(i)} s_i) \prod_{j=1}^{n^{(i)}} \Gamma(1 - a_j^{(i)} + \alpha_j^{(i)} s_i)}{\prod_{j=m^{(i)}+1}^{q^{(i)}} \Gamma(1 - b_j^{(i)} + \beta_j^{(i)} s_i) \prod_{j=n^{(i)}+1}^{p^{(i)}} \Gamma(a_j^{(i)} - \alpha_j^{(i)} s_i)} \quad \forall i \in (1, 2, \dots, r) \quad (1.2)$$

$$\psi(s_1, \dots, s_r) = \frac{\prod_{j=1}^{n_2} \Gamma\left(1 - a_{2j} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \alpha_{2j}^{(i)} s_i\right) \prod_{j=1}^{n_3} \Gamma\left(1 - a_{3j} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_{3j}^{(i)} s_i\right)}{\prod_{j=n_2+1}^{p_2} \Gamma\left(a_{2j} - \sum_{i=1}^2 \alpha_{2j}^{(i)} s_i\right) \prod_{j=n_3+1}^{p_3} \Gamma\left(a_{3j} - \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_{3j}^{(i)} s_i\right)} \dots \prod_{j=1}^{n_r} \Gamma\left(1 - a_{rj} + \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_{rj}^{(i)} s_i\right) \dots \prod_{j=n_r+1}^{p_r} \Gamma\left(a_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_{rj}^{(i)} s_i\right) \prod_{j=1}^{q_2} \Gamma\left(1 - b_{2j} - \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_{2j}^{(i)} s_i\right) \dots \prod_{j=1}^{q_r} \Gamma\left(1 - b_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^r \beta_{rj}^{(i)} s_i\right) \quad (1.3)$$

$\alpha_j^{(i)}, \beta_j^{(i)}, \alpha_{kj}^{(i)}, \beta_{kj}^{(i)} (i = 1, \dots, r) (k = 1, \dots, r)$ are positive numbers,

$a_j^{(i)}, b_j^{(i)} (i = 1, \dots, r), a_{kj}, b_{kj} (k = 2, \dots, r)$ are complex numbers and here

$m^{(i)}, n^{(i)}, p^{(i)}, q^{(i)} (i = 1, \dots, r), n_k, p_k, q_k (k = 2, \dots, r)$ are non-negative integers where

$0 \leq m^{(i)} \leq q^{(i)}, 0 \leq n^{(i)} \leq p^{(i)}, q^k \geq 0, 0 \leq n_k \leq p_k$. Here (i) denotes the numbers of dashes. The

contours L_i in the complex s_i -plane is of the Mellin-Barnes type which runs from $-w\infty$ to $+w\infty$

with indentations, if necessary, to ensure that all the poles of $\Gamma(b_j^{(i)} - \beta_j^{(i)} s_i) (j = 1, \dots, m^{(i)})$ are

separated from those of $\Gamma\left(1 - a_{rj} + \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_{rj}^{(i)} s_i\right) (j = 1, \dots, n_r)$.

For further details and asymptotic expansion of the I -function one can refer by Prasad [5].

In what follows, the multivariable I -function defined by Prasad [5] will be represented in the contracted notation:

$$I_{p_2, q_2, \dots, p_r, q_r; (m', n') \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)})}^{0, n_2, \dots, n_r; (m', n') \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)})} [z_1, \dots, z_r]$$

Or simply by $I[z_1, \dots, z_r]$.

According to the asymptotic expansion of the gamma function, the counter integral (1.1) is absolutely convergent provided that

$$|\arg z_i| < \frac{1}{2} \pi U_i, U_i > 0 ; \quad i=1, 2, \dots, r \quad (1.4)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} U_i = & \sum_{j=1}^{n^i} \alpha_j^{(i)} - \sum_{j=n^{(i)+1}}^{p^{(i)}} \alpha_j^{(i)} + \sum_{j=1}^{m^i} \beta_j^{(i)} - \sum_{j=m^{(i)+1}}^{q^{(i)}} \beta_j^{(i)} \\ & + \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \alpha_{2j}^{(i)} - \sum_{j=n_2+1}^{p_2} \alpha_{2j}^{(i)} \right) + \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_3} \alpha_{3j}^{(i)} - \sum_{j=n_3+1}^{p_3} \alpha_{3j}^{(i)} \right) \\ & + \dots + \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_r} \alpha_{rj}^{(i)} - \sum_{j=n_r+1}^{p_r} \alpha_{rj}^{(i)} \right) \\ & - \left(\sum_{j=1}^{q_2} \beta_{2j}^{(i)} + \sum_{j=1}^{q_3} \beta_{3j}^{(i)} + \dots + \sum_{j=1}^{q_r} \beta_{rj}^{(i)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

The asymptotic expansion of the I -function has been discussed by Prasad [5]. His results run as follow:

$$I[z_1, \dots, z_r] = O(|z_1|^{\alpha_1} \dots |z_r|^{\alpha_r}), \max\{|z_1|, \dots, |z_r|\} \rightarrow 0$$

Where

$$\alpha_i = \min \operatorname{Re}(b_j^{(i)} / \beta_j^{(i)}), \quad j=1, \dots, m^{(i)} ; \quad i=1, \dots, r \quad (1.6)$$

$$\text{And } I[z_1, \dots, z_r] = O(|z_1|^{\beta_1} \dots |z_r|^{\beta_r}), \min\{|z_1|, \dots, |z_r|\} \rightarrow \infty$$

Where

$$\beta_i = \max \operatorname{Re}\left(\frac{a_j^{(i)} - 1}{\alpha_j^{(i)}}\right) ; \quad j=1, \dots, n^{(i)} , i=1, \dots, r \quad (1.7)$$

The details of the function can be found in the paper of Prasad [5].

In this paper we will evaluate an integral involving generalized associated Legendre's function and the multivariable I -function due to Prasad [5] and apply it in deriving an expansion for the multivariable I -function in series of products of associated Legendre's function and the multivariable I -function.

2. THE INTEGRAL

The integral to be evaluated is:

$$\int_{-1}^1 (1-x)^{\rho-\frac{u}{2}} (1+x)^{\sigma+\frac{v}{2}} P_{k-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x) \times I \left[(1-x)^{\alpha_1} (1+x)^{\beta_1} z_1, \dots, (1-x)^{\alpha_r} (1+x)^{\beta_r} z_r \right] dx$$

$$= 2^{\rho-u+v+\sigma+1} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-k)_t (v-u+k+1)_t}{\Gamma(1-u+t) t!} I_{\substack{0, n_2, \dots, 0, n_r+2; (m', n') \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)}) \\ p_2, q_2, \dots, p_r+2, q_r+1; (p', q) \dots; (p^{(r)}, q^{(r)})}}^{u, n_2, \dots, 0, n_r+2; (m', n') \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)})} \left[\begin{matrix} 2^{\alpha_1+\beta_1} z_1 \\ \vdots \\ 2^{\alpha_r+\beta_r} z_r \end{matrix} \left(\begin{matrix} (a_{2j}, \alpha'_{2j}, \alpha''_{2j})_{1, p_2} \dots; (-\sigma-v; \beta_1, \dots, \beta_r), \\ (b_{2j}, \beta'_{2j}, \beta''_{2j})_{1, q_2} \dots; (b_{rj}, \beta'_{rj}, \beta''_{rj})_{1, q_r}, \\ (u-\rho-t; \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r), (\alpha_{ij}, \alpha'_{ij}, \dots, \alpha_{ij}^{(r)})_{1, p_i}; (a_j, \alpha'_j)_{1, p}; \dots; (a_j^{(r)}, \alpha_j^{(r)})_{1, p^{(r)}} \\ (u-v-\rho-\sigma-t-1; \alpha_1+\beta_1, \dots, \alpha_r+\beta_r); (b_j, \beta'_j)_{1, q}; \dots; (b_j^{(r)}, \beta_j^{(r)})_{1, q^{(r)}} \end{matrix} \right) \right] \quad (2.1)$$

The integral (2.1) is valid under the following set of conditions:

(i) $(\alpha_i, \beta_i) > 0; \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}; k - \frac{u-v}{2}$ is a positive integer, k is a integer ≥ 0 .

(ii) $\text{Re} \left(\rho - u + \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_i \frac{b_j^{(i)}}{\beta_j^{(i)}} \right) > -1; \text{Re} \left(\sigma + v + \sum_{i=1}^r \beta_i \frac{b_j^{(i)}}{\beta_j^{(i)}} \right) > -1; (j = 1, 2, \dots, m_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, r)$

And the conditions given in (1.4) to (1.7) are also satisfied.

Proof: On expressing the multivariable I -function in the integrand as a multiple Mellin-Barnes type integral (1.1) and inverting the order of integrations, which is justified due to the absolute convergence of the integrals involved in the process, the value of the integral

$$= (2\pi w)^r \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_r} \psi(s_1, \dots, s_r) \sum_{i=1}^r \left\{ \phi_i(s_i) z_i^{\xi_i} \right\}$$

$$\times \left\{ \int_{-1}^1 (1-x)^{\rho-\frac{u}{2}+\sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_i \xi_i} (1+x)^{\sigma+\frac{v}{2}+\sum_{i=1}^r \beta_i \xi_i} P_{k-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x) dx \right\} d\xi_1 \dots d\xi_r$$

On evaluating the x -integral with the help of the integral ([4], p.343, eq. (38)):

$$\int_{-1}^1 (1-x)^\rho (1+x)^\sigma P_{k-\frac{m-n}{2}}^{m,n}(x) dx$$

$$= \frac{2^{\rho+\sigma-\frac{m-n}{2}} \Gamma\left(\rho-\frac{m}{2}+1\right) \Gamma\left(\sigma+\frac{n}{2}+1\right)}{\Gamma(1-m) \Gamma\left(\rho+\sigma-\frac{m-n}{2}+2\right)} \times {}_3F_2\left(-k, n-m+k+1, \rho-\frac{m}{2}+1; 1-m, \rho-\sigma-\frac{m-n}{2}+2; 1\right) \quad (2.2)$$

Provided that $\text{Re}\left(\rho-\frac{m}{2}\right) > -1$; $\text{Re}\left(\sigma+\frac{n}{2}\right) > -1$ and interpreting the result with the help of (1.1), the integral (2.1) is established.

3. EXPANSION THEOREM

Let the following conditions be established:

- (i) $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_r > 0$; $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r \geq 0$ (or $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_r \geq 0$; $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r > 0$);
- (ii) $m^{(i)}, n^{(i)}, p^{(i)}, q^{(i)}$ ($i=1, \dots, r$), n_k, p_k, q_k ($k=2, \dots, r$) are non-negative integers where $0 \leq m^{(i)} \leq q^{(i)}$, $0 \leq n^{(i)} \leq p^{(i)}$, $q^k \geq 0$, $0 \leq n_k \leq p_k$ and the conditions given by (1.4) to (1.7) are also satisfied.

$$(iii) \text{Re}(u) > -1, \text{Re}(v) > -1, \text{Re}\left(\rho-u+\sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_i \frac{b_j^{(i)}}{\beta_j^{(i)}}\right) > -1;$$

$$\text{Re}\left(\sigma+v+\sum_{i=1}^r \beta_i \frac{b_j^{(i)}}{\beta_j^{(i)}}\right) > -1; (j=1, 2, \dots, m_i; i=1, 2, \dots, r).$$

Then the following expansion formula holds:

$$(1-x)^{\rho-\frac{u}{2}} (1+x)^{\sigma+\frac{v}{2}} I \left[(1-x)^{\alpha_1} (1+x)^{\beta_1} z_1, \dots, (1-x)^{\alpha_r} (1+x)^{\beta_r} z_r \right]$$

$$= 2^{\rho+\sigma} \sum_{N=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\mu=0}^N \frac{(2N-u+v+1) \Gamma(N-u+1) \Gamma(1+v-u+N+\mu) (-N)_{\mu}}{N! \mu! \Gamma(1+v+N) \Gamma(1-u+\mu)}$$

$$P_{N-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x) I_{p_2, q_2, \dots, p_r+2, q_r+1; (p', q) \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)})}^{0, n_2, \dots, n_r+2; (m', n') \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)})} \left[\begin{matrix} 2^{\alpha_1+\beta_1} z_1 \\ \vdots \\ 2^{\alpha_r+\beta_r} z_r \end{matrix} \left| \begin{matrix} (a_{2j}, \alpha_{2j}, \alpha_{2j}^*, \lambda_{p_2} \dots; (-\sigma-v; \beta_1, \dots, \beta_r), \\ (b_{2j}, \beta_{2j}, \beta_{2j}^*, \lambda_{q_2} \dots; (b_{ij}, \beta_{ij}^*, \beta_{ij}^{(r)}) \lambda_{q_r}, \end{matrix} \right. \right.$$

$$\left[\begin{matrix} (u-\rho-\mu; \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r), (\alpha_{ij}, \alpha'_{ij}, \dots, \alpha_{ij}^{(r)})_{1, p_r}; (a_j, \alpha'_j)_{1, p} \dots; (a_j^{(r)}, \alpha_j^{(r)})_{1, p(r)} \\ (u-v-\rho-\sigma-\mu-1; \alpha_1 + \beta_1, \dots, \alpha_r + \beta_r), (b_j, \beta'_j)_{1, q} \dots; (b_j^{(r)}, \beta_j^{(r)})_{1, q(r)} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (3.1)$$

Proof: Let

$$f(x) = (1-x)^{\rho-\frac{u}{2}} (1+x)^{\sigma+\frac{v}{2}} I \left[(1-x)^{\alpha_1} (1+x)^{\beta_1} z_1, \dots, (1-x)^{\alpha_r} (1+x)^{\beta_r} z_r \right]$$

$$= \sum_{N=0}^{\infty} C_N P_{N-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x) \quad (3.2)$$

Equation (3.2) is valid since $f(x)$ is continuous and of bounded variation in the interval $(-1,1)$.

Now, multiplying both the sides of (3.2) by $P_{N-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x)$ and integrating with respect to x from -1 to

1 ; evaluating the L.H.S. with the help of (2.1) and on the R.H.S. interchanging the order of summation, using ([2],p.176,eq. (75)) and then applying orthogonality property of the generalized Legendre's associated functions ([4],p.340,eq.(27)):

$$\int_{-1}^1 P_{k-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x) P_{N-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x) dx$$

$$= \begin{cases} 0; & \text{if } k \neq N \\ \frac{2^{u-v+1} k! \Gamma(k+v+1)}{(2k-u+v+1) \Gamma(k-u+1) \Gamma(k-u+v+1)}; & \text{if } k=N \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

Provided that $\text{Re}(u), 1, \text{Re}(v) < 1$; we obtain

$$C_k = \frac{2^{\rho+\sigma} (2k-u+v+1) \Gamma(k-u+1)}{k! \Gamma(k+v+1)} \sum_{\mu=0}^k \frac{(-k)_{\mu} \Gamma(k-u+v+\mu+1)}{\mu! \Gamma(k-u+\mu)}$$

$$I_{\substack{0, n_2, \dots, 0, n_r+2; (m', n') \dots; (m^{(r)}, n^{(r)}) \\ p_2, q_2, \dots, p_r+2, q_r+1; (p', q') \dots; (p^{(r)}, q^{(r)})}} \left[\begin{matrix} 2^{\alpha_1+\beta_1} z_1 & (a_{2j}, \alpha'_{2j}, \alpha_{2j})_{1, p_2} \dots; (-\sigma-v; \beta_1, \dots, \beta_r), \\ \vdots \\ 2^{\alpha_r+\beta_r} z_r & (b_{2j}, \beta'_{2j}, \beta_{2j})_{1, q_2} \dots; (b_{ij}, \beta'_{ij}, \dots, \beta_{ij}^{(r)})_{1, q_r}, \end{matrix} \right]$$

$$\left[\begin{matrix} (u-\rho-\mu; \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r), (\alpha_{ij}, \alpha'_{ij}, \dots, \alpha_{ij}^{(r)})_{1, p_r}; (a_j, \alpha'_j)_{1, p} \dots; (a_j^{(r)}, \alpha_j^{(r)})_{1, p(r)} \\ (u-v-\rho-\sigma-\mu-1; \alpha_1 + \beta_1, \dots, \alpha_r + \beta_r), (b_j, \beta'_j)_{1, q} \dots; (b_j^{(r)}, \beta_j^{(r)})_{1, q(r)} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (3.4)$$

Now on substituting the values of C_k in (3.2), the result follows.

4. SPECIAL CASES

If in (2.1), we put $n_2 = \dots = n_{r-1} = 0 = p_2 = \dots = p_{r-1}, q_2 = \dots = q_{r-1} = 0$, the multivariable I - function reduces to multivariable H -function and we get result given by Saxena and Ramawat [6]

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (1-x)^{\rho-\frac{u}{2}}(1+x)^{\sigma+\frac{v}{2}} H \left[(1-x)^{\alpha_1} (1+x)^{\beta_1} z_1, \dots, (1-x)^{\alpha_r} (1+x)^{\beta_r} z_r \right] \\
 &= 2^{\rho+\sigma} \sum_{N=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\mu=0}^N \frac{(2N-u+v+1)\Gamma(N-u+1)\Gamma(1+v-u+N+\mu)(-N)_{\mu}}{N! \mu! \Gamma(1+v+N)\Gamma(1-u+\mu)} \\
 & P_{N-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x) H_{p+2,q+1(p',q') \dots (p^{(r)},q^{(r)})}^{0,n+2:(m',n') \dots (m^{(r)},n^{(r)})} \\
 & \left[\begin{matrix} 2^{\alpha_1+\beta_1} z_1 & \left(\begin{matrix} -\sigma-v; \beta_1, \dots, \beta_r \end{matrix} \right) \\ \vdots \\ 2^{\alpha_r+\beta_r} z_r & \left(\begin{matrix} b_j, \beta_j, \dots, \beta_j^{(r)} \end{matrix} \right)_{1,q} \end{matrix} \right] \\
 & \left. \begin{matrix} (u-\rho-\mu; \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r), (\alpha_j, \alpha_j', \dots, \alpha_j^{(r)})_{1,p}, (\alpha_j, \alpha_j', \dots, \alpha_j^{(r)})_{1,p} \dots (\alpha_j^{(r)}, \alpha_j^{(r)})_{1,p^{(r)}} \\ (u-v-\rho-\sigma-\mu-1; \alpha_1+\beta_1, \dots, \alpha_r+\beta_r), (b_j, \beta_j)_{1,q} \dots (b_j^{(r)}, \beta_j^{(r)})_{1,q^{(r)}} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (4.1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Provided all the conditions given with (3.1) and the conditions ([7], p.252-253, eq. (c.4), (c.5) and (c.6)) are satisfied.

For $n = 0 = p, q = 0$, the multivariable H -function breaks up into a product of r H -function and consequently, (4.1) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (1-x)^{\rho-\frac{u}{2}}(1+x)^{\sigma+\frac{v}{2}} \prod_{i=1}^r \left\{ H_{p_i, q_i}^{m_i, n_i} \left[(1-x)^{\alpha_i} (1+x)^{\beta_i} \left(\begin{matrix} a_j^{(i)}, \alpha_j^{(i)} \\ b_j^{(i)}, \beta_j^{(i)} \end{matrix} \right)_{1, p_i} \right] \right\} \\
 &= 2^{\rho+\sigma} \sum_{N=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\mu=0}^N \frac{(2N-u+v+1)\Gamma(N-u+1)\Gamma(1+v-u+N+\mu)(-N)_{\mu}}{N! \mu! \Gamma(1+v+N)\Gamma(1-u+\mu)} \\
 & P_{N-\frac{u-v}{2}}^{u,v}(x) H_{2,1:(p',q') \dots (p^{(r)},q^{(r)})}^{0,2:(m',n') \dots (m^{(r)},n^{(r)})} \left[\begin{matrix} 2^{\alpha_1+\beta_1} z_1 & \left(\begin{matrix} -\sigma-v; \beta_1, \dots, \beta_r \end{matrix} \right) \\ \vdots \\ 2^{\alpha_r+\beta_r} z_r & \left(\begin{matrix} b_j, \beta_j, \dots, \beta_j^{(r)} \end{matrix} \right)_{1,q} \end{matrix} \right] \\
 & \left. \begin{matrix} (u-\rho-\mu; \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r), (\alpha_j, \alpha_j')_{1,p} \dots (\alpha_j^{(r)}, \alpha_j^{(r)})_{1,p^{(r)}} \\ (u-v-\rho-\sigma-\mu-1; \alpha_1+\beta_1, \dots, \alpha_r+\beta_r), (b_j, \beta_j)_{1,q} \dots (b_j^{(r)}, \beta_j^{(r)})_{1,q^{(r)}} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (4.2)
 \end{aligned}$$

For $r = 1$, (4.2) gives riseto the result due to Anandani [1].

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